

**UNIVERSITY OF THE PHILIPPINES
OPEN UNIVERSITY**

Master of Information Systems

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**WEB-BASED INTERNSHIP MANAGEMENT SYSTEM
FOR LYCEUM OF THE PHILIPPINES UNIVERSITY - CAVITE**

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Date of Submission

10 December 2021

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This Special Project titled

WEB-BASED INTERNSHIP MANAGEMENT SYSTEM
FOR LYCEUM OF THE PHILIPPINES UNIVERSITY - CAVITE

is hereby accepted by the Faculty of Information and Communication Studies in partial fulfillment of the requirements for the Master of Information Systems.

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ABSTRACT

One of the missions of Lyceum of the Philippines University – Cavite (LPU – Cavite) is to provide equitable access to learning through relevant, innovative, industry-based, and environment-conscious programs and services for their stakeholders. The internship is one of the programs of the University that provides students the opportunity to determine their career goals, apply the knowledge they have acquired from the University, and secure their network and good recommendations before they graduate. Being mentioned how important an internship is, LPU – Cavite is expected to have an efficient procedure and an effective system that could support the program throughout the years. However, it is discovered that the University is using the traditional manual system with the process of the internship.

After a thorough review of the existing procedures, the proponent proposed to apply digital modernization to the current process. A web-based internship management system was developed to eliminate problems that are caused by the manual procedure and provide the client definite solutions and improve the customer service quality that they can offer to their stakeholders. The system aims to bring convenience to the students, create easier communication between the affiliated Host Training Establishments and students, and provide a platform for efficient monitoring of the submitted documents and handling of reports.

However, the proponent excluded the integration of the grading system into the management system as there is still an existing protocol that needs a separate study on how both systems can co-exist with one another.

Additionally, it must be known that all reports generated by the system are patterned with the existing templates used by the client. Should there be any changes in the future must be coordinated with the Information and Technology Department, which will maintain the system, for any revisions.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

The journey towards the season finale of this educational and career advancement is challenging and overwhelming, to say the least. Within the two and a half years of pursuance to the goal, a lot of things have happened may it be unfortunate events or simple wins in life. There were a lot of times we wanted to leave the dream behind and not proceed anymore but we ended up still pushing through. Definitely, a big part of why we are standing still despite a lot of what-ifs are the people who motivate and help us along the way. These people are my source of gravity, keeping me steady while my world is unraveling of doubts.

First and foremost, I want to express my utmost gratitude to Almighty God for everything He has given me – wisdom, guidance, and a sense of security throughout the conception of this paper. Despite these challenging times, my faith in Him keeps me going, knowing He won't fail me, and He'll be there for me and my family.

Second, to my family who is my source of inspiration and my anchor on this journey. They fuel my will to finish what I have started. My momma raises no quitter in this family, that's for sure. The unconditional love they have for me helps me to persevere harder. They are my constant reminder of why I am on this journey. All my achievements are dedicated to them.

Third, my friends and co-workers who never doubt me and provide me with never-ending encouragement since day one. They are my number one fan. My "budol" friends and food panda buddies, Anna and Aiza. My best friend, Rian, who stands by

my side any day any time. My mentor, Engr. Laarnie Carlos, who always makes herself available for our “consultation”. She provides insights into my research but as well, challenges me to do better. To my internet friend and cheerleader, Luna. Conversations with you have no in-between – either we are both on a high or just seriously conversing with pop culture.

Fourth, to the University that is not only my client but my workplace for letting me juggle my duties as your employee and my studies smoothly. To my ever-supportive team leaders, Dr. Elmer Matel, Ms. Miriam Abayan, and Mr. Regil Vergara, who constantly support me and remind me that I am on the right path.

And lastly, to the University of the Philippines – Open University, it is an honor to be called one of your students. Thank you for accepting my application and believing in what I can bring to the table. To all my instructors for the past five semesters, to Dr. Ria Borromeo, my research adviser. Please accept my sincere gratitude for honing my skills more and imparting a huge amount of knowledge.

TABLE OF CONTENTS

ABSTRACT	5
ACKNOWLEDGMENTS	7
TABLE OF CONTENTS	9
Chapter I: Introduction	1
Chapter II: Review of Existing Alternatives	4
Chapter III: Project Details	8
Chapter IV: Project Assessment	22
Chapter V: Discussion	30
Chapter VI: Conclusion	33
Chapter VII: Future Work	35
REFERENCES	38
APPENDICES	40
System Usability Scale (SUS)	40
Source Code	42
User Manual Documentation	43

Dedicated to:
to my family.

To God be the glory.

Chapter I

INTRODUCTION

On-the-job training (OJT) or Internship aims to provide students with opportunities to apply relevant knowledge and skills acquired from formal education to actual work settings provided by reputable Host Training Establishments (HTEs) in the country. This allows the students to gain work experience from reputable HTEs and get exposed to the industry they have chosen before graduation. It is the best time to step out of their comfort zone, from the four walls of the classroom, learn from the professionals on how to be a good team player, cope up in the workspace, and develop a work ethic. Thus, it is evident how an internship can provide a good number of opportunities to improve the student's technical and social skills.

Additionally, the role of the University is important in creating this kind of opportunity for its student. The University needs to establish good relationships with the HTEs to deliver a proper internship experience. For instance, the Lyceum of the Philippines University – Cavite created a centralized department dedicated to the internship, called the Center for Career Services and Industry Relations (CCSIR). The Center aims to be the bridge between the students and the HTEs. They intend to communicate with these companies and form partnerships to provide the students with the best option for their internship. Universities such as LPU, need a strategic approach on how they can deliver excellent quality services and extend their support system to their stakeholders in the most effective and efficient way possible. In a research about the potential power of internships and the impact on career preparation, it is concluded that *“Universities must expand and enhance their respective placements in organizational sites where partnerships can flourish”*

(Galbraith, 2020). The study firmly confirms that establishing networks and linkages can give a significant difference between one's internship experience. Not only it is mutually beneficial for both of the institutions, but it could build one's future when a partnership is done right and communicated thoroughly.

However, having a mutual association with different HTE is just one of the steps in creating a better process towards internship. The University must have a systematized of organizing internship procedures for students to follow. The Center, which was founded in 2014, is using manual processing of documents and transactions since then. Years of depending on its manual process might affect how they can deal with the internship process. Problems might occur and it would not be advisable in the long run. In the year of technological advancement, institutions must maximize its use and explore the pros and cons that it could bring to their business. Technology has reshaped the way a business handles different barriers like communication, task performance, management, or outsourcing. The availability of different software and applications can provide options on how one's business can upgrade its operational procedures. This can minimize the struggles and impending complications that the manual process causes.

Further, this presents an opportunity for the proponent to conduct a proposal on how the Center can enhance the existing procedure without affecting the core of the

services they have been providing to their stakeholders. The proponent shall submit design options that could eliminate the dilemma the Center is currently facing and provide a platform that will address the issue. Through this, the Center can continuously provide better services to its stakeholders.

Chapter II

REVIEW OF EXISTING ALTERNATIVES

The Center has been accustomed to the use of a manual processing system incorporated into the process of Internship. They have laid out their guidelines and procedures to match what they think is best for the stakeholders. They follow a well-documented guideline, based on CHED's protocol, that defines criteria how to select the best HTEs for the students, defining the eligibility of one student to enroll in practicum, and crediting of learning activities and past or current employment that is related to student's specialization.

The Center needs at least two to three (2-3) months of preparation before the internship starts. The time being is needed to accomplish the following activities: reproduction of materials to be used by the students, coordination to HTEs with regards to their vacancies, orienting the students with the guidelines and procedures, and setting timelines on when students must submit their documents before the internship. Additionally, pre-training documentation isn't the only dilemma for the Center. Post-training documentation is as complicated as the former, as students' documents are needed during university accreditation. The process of storing a big volume of papers properly, in an attempt to create organized storage of documents, is hard work for the staff. However, a retention policy is being applied to these documents so they can dispose of them after a specific year just to make room for another bulk of papers.

Through a thorough study of the current process used by the Center, the proponent concluded that the Center could use a more fluid management system that helps the Center to establish a strong, sharp, accurate monitoring and/or managing of student's internship status and documents submitted. Additionally, it must have a platform that lets the coordinators, students, and HTEs to communicate with each other which would support a faster, easier, and efficient way of processing internships. Reforming the existing system would only be bound to provide solutions that would fit the business processes done by the Center and not override nor completely change the entire process.

Further, since the proponent decides to develop a web-based management system for the internship, it is vital before the project proceeds, to establish a line between other researches. The developing system should not be existing in the research directory and the project's system functions will not resemble any existing system that is similar to the proponent's proposal. To do so, the proponent lays out an analysis of the different existing web-based systems for internship and compares them to the proposed system. In this way, the proponent can prove the need to develop the said system.

Internships Management System (2016)

The system creates an easy environment for the University that could help them to improve the procedures of an internship. The developed system is built to automate the process of collecting, reviewing, and managing applications for internships and the ongoing lifecycle of the project. Though the system covers the majority of what the

proponent intended to develop, the connection between the students and their possible employer is lacking for this developed system.

Web-Based Application of the Internship Management System (2017)

This internship management system is developed to solve the problem that occurred among students, coordinators, and employers. It speeds up the process of finding internship slots and a possible employer by giving recommendations from the pool of registered employers suitable for them based on their qualifications. However, the system focuses only on the connection between the employer and the students. The said system does not include the process of an internship between the officers of the University and the students.

Internship Monitoring and Supervising Web-Based System (2017)

The developed system includes one of the objectives of the proposed system which is to create a medium that eases the communication between the students and the University on processing their internship documents. Despite the similarity, the system was built to monitor a certain program. With this, certain functionalities do not cover the objectives of the proposed system.

Internship Management System (2020)

The system facilitates the process of application for internship positions for students and employers. It advertises vacancies and eliminates manual processes. But the scope of this system is limited to the process of actual training ground between the students and the employer. The existing system does not include the documentation to be made before the training.

Chapter III

PROJECT DETAILS

A. Overview

The proponent developed a web-based internship management system that can provide a digital solution to the manual processing system of CCSIR. The system provided easier transactions between the students, the industry partners, and the business operators, themselves. Its focus is to eliminate the tedious and paper-dependent process of internship and maximize the use of technology that could help the organization to provide better services to its stakeholders without compromising its objectives.

8 *Figure 1. Use Case Diagram of Web-based Internship Management System for LPU - Cavite*

Figure 1 depicts the functional requirements of the system. It captures how users will interact with the system and how these modules are interconnected with each other. The diagram explains the flow of the system and the role of the actors, which are the users, in the system.

B. Theoretical Framework

Figure 2. The theoretical framework for the Web-Based Internship Management System for LPU - Cavite

The proponent decides to use this framework to show the relationship of the variables presented in this project. The proponent may use diagrams under this framework to illustrate the concepts and processes that will be encountered throughout the development of the system.

The input-process-output (IPO) model is chosen to be the visual diagram for this project as it depicts the process in its simplest form. The model has four phases to meet the objectives stated above by the proponents.

The first part stated in the diagram is the input phase wherein it includes the needed requirements to start with the project. The first phase includes the knowledge, software, and hardware requirements. Knowledge requirements specify the data and information gathered from the Center – the business process and every document and template they have been using with regards to the internship. This information will not only serve as the food of the system but also the guide on how the system can adapt to the process. The proponent must have at least knowledge of how the manual system flows and the documents it is associated with, to perform the modernization of the existing process. In this part, software and hardware requirements are being specified as a prerequisite to the system.

Once the inputs are gathered, the proponent will start to outline the system process. Activities include for this phase are system design, system prototyping, system testing, and debugging. In this phase, the proponent will now incorporate the manual processing system's data into the proposed system to establish the core of the system. The proponent will begin designing modules that match the Center's

requirements and may add features that could enhance the existing system. These modules must be interconnected with each other to create a smoother flow in the process. System testing and evaluation is an important measure in this phase as this would be helpful to test the compatibility and how equipped the system is to human instructions. The Center may call for more features to fit into, but it would be the discretion of the developer if found justifiable to add.

Lastly, once the input-process cycle is done, the proposed system must be in the implementation cycle already. The proponent must confirm that the developed system suits up with the objectives mentioned above and the outcome of the project resolves the problem of the Center. This manner would satisfy the purpose of this project and proves the effectiveness of the digitalization of any manual system.

C. Technologies Used

- **Application Layer**

The proponent used the Hypertext transfer protocol (HTTP) as the application layer to be used in this proposed internship management system. Technopedia.com defines HTTP “*as a fundamental protocol used on the Internet in order to control data transfer to and from a hosting server, in communication with a web browser*”. Since the proponent makes use of the web technology, this protocol will serve as a medium between the users of the system and the servers that maintain the system. This protocol offers an additional layer of security as all data that passes through it will be encrypted.

- **Database Layer**

To adhere to the proposed web-based internship management system, the chosen application's storage platform *"must be reliable for storing information securely and able to easily retrieve any data whenever needed"* (Webxloo, 2021). PHP and MYSQL go hand-in-hand as it is capable of delivering high-quality solutions that benefit web application development. In addition, Jobsity.com lists down different benefits of the relational database management system which includes high compatibility with a wide range of systems, maintains its reputation as being the most reliable database server, uses a variety of backup and recovery strategies to ensure its user that all data are secured, and being able to defend its data from cyberattacks. Thus, it is not quite surprising that this DBMS still holds the top spot for the most popular database technology in 2020 according to a Stack Overflow Developer Survey.

- **Client Layer**

In order to create web dynamic pages that support modules intended to establish a web-based internship management system, the proponent chose to explore the concept of JQuery, Javascript, and CSS for the client-side and PHP for the server-side. This technique allows the proponent to prepare the server for data storage and enhance the overall user interface, as well.

JQuery offers different instant plugins that help the designs to look better with a little tweak of CSS. It is easy to learn as it requires simple syntax to deploy a single web page. While PHP is flexible and supports DBMS systems that ensure a secured connection.

D. System Design

- **System Features**

This part features the graphical user interface of the web-based internship management system. All the modules created by the proponent that was developed in response to the need of the client for a management system.

a. Homepage

The main interface welcomes the users of the system. It contains the basic information of the Center – the services it offers, the team composition, a guide on the step-by-step procedures of internship, and how to contact the Center for further clarification. Should the users do already have their respective accounts, they can use the log-in feature to explore the content of the system.

b. Login Page

WEB·IMS f BACK TO HOME

LOG IN

Username: *

Password:

Login

[Forgot Password?](#)
Don't have an account? [sign up](#)

A centralized log-in page for all the users that requires a username and a password.

c. Users Management

WEB·IMS Hello, Admin f LOGOUT

HOME CONFIGURATION LOGOUT

Users

Displays all users of the system - students, administrators, and industry partners

Select Role Filter Add

Show 10 entries Search:

No	First Name	Last Name	Username	Action
1	Manager	Manager	manager@lpu.edu.ph	View Edit Archive Delete
2	Staff	Staff	staff@lpu.edu.ph	View Edit Archive Delete
3	Hye Young	Ryu	hyeyoung.ryu@lpunetwork.edu.ph	View Edit Archive Delete
4	Bbeom	Kim	bbeom.kim@lpunetwork.edu.ph	View Edit Archive Delete
5	JuanA	Dela Cruz	employer@lpu.edu.ph	View Edit Archive Delete

This module lets the administrator and staff of the Center modify the user's information.

d. Orientation Module

WEB·IMS Hello, Manager [f](#) [@](#)

[HOME](#)
[INTERNSHIP PORTAL](#)
[JOB PORTAL](#)
[REPORTS](#)
[CONFIGURATION](#)
[LOGOUT](#)

Orientation Record

Manages the records of current and past orientation

Select Academic Term

Show entries Search:

No	Academic Term	Venue	Date	Time	Action
1	Second Semester AY 2021 - 2022	Lemon Grass Studio	November 08, 2021	08:00 AM - 05:00 PM	<input type="button" value="Edit"/> <input type="button" value="Hide"/> <input type="button" value="Delete"/>
2	Second Semester AY 2021 - 2022	University Auditorium	November 09, 2021	08:00 AM - 05:00 PM	<input type="button" value="Edit"/> <input type="button" value="Hide"/> <input type="button" value="Delete"/>
3	First Semester AY 2020 - 2021	University Auditorium	October 12, 2021	08:00 AM - 05:00 PM	<input type="button" value="Edit"/> <input type="button" value="Delete"/>
4	First Semester AY 2020 - 2021	Lemon Grass Studio	October 11, 2021	08:00 AM - 05:00 PM	<input type="button" value="Edit"/> <input type="button" value="Delete"/>
5	First Semester AY 2021 - 2022	Lemon Grass Studio	October 13, 2021	08:00 AM - 05:00 PM	<input type="button" value="Edit"/> <input type="button" value="Delete"/>
6	First Semester AY 2021 - 2022	University Auditorium	October 14, 2021	08:00 AM - 05:00 PM	<input type="button" value="Edit"/> <input type="button" value="Delete"/>
7	Second Semester AY 2020 - 2021	University Auditorium	December 07, 2020	12:00 AM - 11:30 PM	<input type="button" value="Edit"/> <input type="button" value="Delete"/>

This module allows the Center to set up the Orientation details and view the attendees for documentation purposes.

e. Internship Templates Module

WEB·IMS Hello, Manager [f](#) [@](#)

[HOME](#)
[INTERNSHIP PORTAL](#)
[JOB PORTAL](#)
[REPORTS](#)
[CONFIGURATION](#)
[LOGOUT](#)

Templates

Manages templates that will be used for internship

Show entries Search:

No	Template Name	Template Description	Template Category	Action
1	A	A	Prelim	<input type="button" value="View"/> <input type="button" value="Edit"/> <input type="button" value="Hide"/> <input type="button" value="Delete"/>
2	C2	C2	Midterm	<input type="button" value="View"/> <input type="button" value="Edit"/> <input type="button" value="Hide"/> <input type="button" value="Delete"/>
3	D	D	Finals	<input type="button" value="View"/> <input type="button" value="Edit"/> <input type="button" value="Hide"/> <input type="button" value="Delete"/>
4	b	b	Prelim	<input type="button" value="View"/> <input type="button" value="Edit"/> <input type="button" value="Publish"/> <input type="button" value="Delete"/>
5	E	E	Prelim	<input type="button" value="View"/> <input type="button" value="Edit"/> <input type="button" value="Publish"/> <input type="button" value="Delete"/>

This module allows the Center to upload and modify the internship templates needed by the students throughout the program.

f. Linkage module

WEB·IMS Hello, Manager [f](#) [@](#)

HOME INTERNSHIP PORTAL **JOB PORTAL** REPORTS CONFIGURATION LOGOUT

Company Profile

Displays the list of affiliated industry partners

[Add](#)

Show entries Search:

No	Company Name	Company Address	Job Listings	Status	Action
1	Leentech Network System	Tanza, Cavite	0	Active	View Edit Archive Delete

The module allows the Center to add and modify affiliated HTEs into the system to post their internship listings for students

g. Internship Application module

WEB·IMS Hello, Staff [f](#) [@](#)

HOME **INTERNSHIP MODULE** REPORTS CONFIGURATION LOGOUT

Internship Application Record

Displays all application of the students

Select Academic Term Select College Select Status [Filter](#)

Show entries Search:

No	Application Number	Student Number	College	Academic Term	Status	Action
1	CCSIR-2021-001	2009-2-88995	CON	Second Semester, AY 2021 - 2022	Disapproved	View
2	CCSIR-2021-002	2009-2-88995	CON	Second Semester, AY 2021 - 2022	Approved	View

This module allows the Center to view and act on internship applications made by the students.

h. Student module

This module consists of the following: registering for the orientation, application of internship documents to the University and the HTE, and uploading of requirements intended for final submission.

Figure 3. Feature of the system that allows the student to register their attendance to the Orientation and downloads the certificate right after.

Figure 4. Feature of the system that allows the student to submit their profile for internship eligibility along with supporting documents needed.

Figure 5. Feature of the system that allows the student to choose from the internship vacancies posted by the affiliated HTEs.

- **Database Design**

The proponent designs the database depending on the information that was collected during the data gathering. To create an easier relationship between different data tables, the proponent draws possible entities for every table and normalizes them.

To easily display the relationship of each table, the proponent divides the database into groups that have a direct connection to each other. Through the use of phpMyAdmin as a third-party tool to “*handle the administration of MySQL over the Web*”, the proponent can generate a logical data model of the web-based system.

Figure 6. Displays the data model of the internship application table which connects the user data table and the tables relating to internships such as the internship templates and internship hours

Figure 7. Displays the data model of the internship orientation table which connects the user data table, venue data table, and the academic term data table.

Figure 8. Displays the data model of users which has three connecting data tables that feature three more connected data tables that exposes more relevant information of the student.

Figure 9. Displays the job application table which connects to the different job listings of each Host Training Establishment.

E. Implementation

During the interview with the Center, the proponent lays out its plan on how to implement the system once it's already developed and approved by the Center and the University, itself. Since this involved revising or upgrading an existing procedure, it will depend on the Center if this will be pushed through for implementation based on the performance of the developed system on how it will react to the stakeholder's actions. It will also go hand-in-hand with how the Center can easily adapt to the system. In response to this, the proponent will conduct pieces of training to the staff of the Center to familiarize themselves with the flow of the system. Meanwhile, an orientation for the students, discussing how the newly developed system will affect the existing procedure, is a must. It is necessary as well for the proponent to coordinate with the Center how they can reorganize the existing procedure to fit the developed system.

Chapter IV

PROJECT ASSESSMENT

A. User Testing

The testing covered the test of the functionality and features of the system. The system was evaluated by the IT experts and non-IT experts such as students at the university, a sample number of industry partners, and the Center's staff. Below are the objectives of the test plan:

- To test and evaluate the features and processes of the system.
- To identify what area of the system needs to improve.
- To determine what are the errors and failures of the system.
- To determine if the system complies with the requirements specified by the target users.

a. Methodology

For the evaluation criterion, the evaluation System Usability Scale (SUS) was used. SUS *provides a "quick and dirty", reliable tool for measuring the usability of any system*" (Usability.gov, n. D). The proponent had chosen the said tool in order for them to evaluate the client's experience when accessing the system and how usable they think it is when implemented. Though the tool is not diagnostic, it can give you a quick evaluation and judgment of how usable your system is. It can determine the effectiveness, efficiency, and satisfaction of the client.

The tool has a scale of 1 to 5 based on how much they agreed with the statement with 5 being tagged as completely agreed, while 1 as disagreed. Gathered data were tabulated and calculated using statistical computations. Tables 1 and 2 show the scoring system and the corresponding interpretations respectively.

Numerical Rating	Equivalent
1.00 – 1.80	Strongly Disagree
1.81 – 2.60	Disagree
2.61 – 3.40	Neutral
3.41 - 4.20	Agree
4.21 – 5.00	Strongly Agree

Table 1. Scoring System

Grade	SUS	Percentile range	Adjective	Acceptable	NPS
A+	84.1-100	96-100	Best Imaginable	Acceptable	Promoter
A	80.8-84.0	90-95	Excellent	Acceptable	Promoter
A-	78.9-80.7	85-89		Acceptable	Promoter
B+	77.2-78.8	80-84		Acceptable	Passive
B	74.1 – 77.1	70 – 79		Acceptable	Passive
B-	72.6 – 74.0	65 – 69		Acceptable	Passive
C+	71.1 – 72.5	60 – 64	Good	Acceptable	Passive
C	65.0 – 71.0	41 – 59		Marginal	Passive
C-	62.7 – 64.9	35 – 40		Marginal	Passive
D	51.7 – 62.6	15 – 34	OK	Marginal	Detractor
F	25.1 – 51.6	2– 14	Poor	Not Acceptable	Detractor
F	0-25	0-19	Worst Imaginable	Not Acceptable	Detractor

Table 2. SUS Interpretation Scale

b. Evaluation Instrument

The system was evaluated using these 10 questionnaires and respondents can mark if they agree or disagree with the following statement depending on the quality and usability of the system:

1. I think that I would like to use this system frequently.
2. I found the system unnecessarily complex.
3. I thought the system was easy to use.
4. I think that I would need the support of a technical person to be able to use this system.
5. I found the various functions in this system were well integrated.
6. I thought there was too much inconsistency in this system.
7. I would imagine that most people would learn to use this system very quickly.
8. I found the system very cumbersome to use.
9. I felt very confident using the system.
10. I needed to learn a lot of things before I could get going with this system.

c. Testing Results

The system's usability was evaluated through the SUS questionnaire by a sample of the population from LPU – Cavite students, the Center's staff, and an IT professional.

Item	Mean	Equivalent
I think that I would like to use this system frequently.	4.70	Strongly Agree
I found the system unnecessarily complex.	1.60	Strongly Disagree
I thought the system was easy to use.	4.80	Strongly Agree
I think that I would need the support of a technical person to be able to use this system.	2.20	Disagree
I found the various functions in this system were well integrated.	4.70	Strongly Agree
I thought there was too much inconsistency in this system.	1.30	Strongly Disagree
I would imagine that most people would learn to use this system very quickly.	4.70	Strongly Agree
I found the system very cumbersome to use.	1.80	Strongly Disagree
I felt very confident using the system.	4.90	Strongly Agree
I needed to learn a lot of things before I could get going with this system.	1.90	Disagree

Table 3 displays the mean output of every question and its equivalent

Question No.	SUS Raw Score	Final SUS Score	Grade	Over-all Usability Adjective
1	37	92.50	A+	Best Imaginable
2	36	90.00	A+	Best Imaginable
3	35	87.50	A+	Best Imaginable
4	29	72.50	B+	Excellent
5	24	60.00	A	Excellent
6	35	87.50	A+	Best Imaginable
7	39	97.50	A+	Best Imaginable
8	32	80.00	A-	Excellent
9	31	77.50	B+	Excellent
10	36	90.00	A+	Best Imaginable
Overall SUS		87.50	A+	Best Imaginable

Table 4 exhibits the computation using a scoring tabulation methodology that will determine the final score of the system on the System Usability Scale

d. Summary of Findings

According to the analysis of the results of the Internship Management System from the respondents after evaluating the system, the SUS score of 87.50 shows that the system is at its best imaginable version there is. The system is functioning well, and its interface is user-friendly.

In addition to it, the following findings were formed:

1. The respondents/user would like to use the system frequently.
2. The system is not unnecessarily complex.
3. The system is easy to use.
4. The respondents/user would not need the support of a technical person to be able to use the system.
5. The functions in the system were well integrated.
6. There was no inconsistency found in the system.
7. Most users would learn to use this system very quickly.
8. The system is not at all cumbersome to use.
9. The user will have confidence in using the system because it is easy to navigate.
10. There is no need to learn a lot of things before the user could get going with the system.

B. Security Testing

Web-based applications must not only be tested on the functionality and interface of their features, but developers must consider the vulnerability of the system and how it can handle attacks to protect the data stored in its database. Security testing is being referred to as the process of gauging the security strength using manual and automated techniques. The test can identify all loopholes and expose the weakness of the developed web application system that may result in loss of information, revenue, and even the reputation of the organization.

a. Methodology

Security Testing covers different testing that focuses on different aspects of the web application. For this study, the proponent uses Security Scanning to identify network and system weaknesses and be able to provide solutions that can eliminate or if not, minimize the risks for its stakeholders. Since the developed system collects sensitive data from the students and accredited establishments, it will be targeted by the attacks. Thus, the developers need to secure their web applications by conducting a series of security of tests before the system will be implemented and handed over to the clients.

One of the popular security scanners that can safeguard the sensitive data stored in the system is the open-source web application security scanner called OWASP ZAP. The application can help the developers to point vulnerabilities on their systems by deploying spider attacks that would try to bypass the current security of your system. Once a loophole has been exposed, it will generate reports for a possible solution that is needed to apply to the system.

b. Testing Results

After an automated scan of the system, the OWASP displays the following alerts that need to be addressed:

- Cross-Site Scripting is an attack technique that involves echoing attacker-supplied code into a user's browser instance. It is also

mentioned that to address the problem, the developer must use a vetted library or framework that does not allow the weakness to be revealed.

The architecture and design of the system must be improved.

- SQL injection on one web page. It was exposed that the page results were successfully manipulated by a Boolean condition. The developer must know that it is best to separate the data from SQL for the data to not be interpreted as commands. Using PDO and MySQLi are presented as options for dealing with this attack.
- The developer must ensure that the web server, application server, etc. must be set to the proper Content-Security-Policy header.
- Outdated Javascript library
- Disable directory browsing

Moving forward, the aforementioned security issues will be handled by the developer before the deployment of the system. It is important to address the following issues firsthand to avoid problems that will arise if this remains untouched.

Chapter V

DISCUSSIONS

The main objective of this research is to eliminate the problems caused by the manual processing system. It aims to create a more fluid management system that helps accredited employers, and University officials to manage internships conveniently and efficiently, and connects them to the student easily. The application of digital modernization will provide the client with a definite solution to the existing dilemma.

The development of this research incites different challenges to the proponent; however, these threats were turned to be ideas that assisted the study to progress and helped to attain its set goals. The following were the insights of the proponent during the conduct of the study:

1. Revising an existing procedure with the use of technology is never an easy feat. The proponent must make sure that every single procedure is part of the digitization. Should there be any changes or part of the process that is needed to omit, it should be consulted to the client and must be presented with the explanations on why there will be changes. The proponent must also be careful not to revamp the whole procedure but rather, just to implement advancement to the current procedure as there will be documents that will be compromised.

2. Clients will be hesitant at first to the implementation of the system but presented findings on how the developed system can improve its services to its stakeholders will be the turnaround point of the system.
3. Business owners must maximize the use of technology in their business. Digital modernization can play an important role in the success of the business.
4. Universities are critical of new advancements for their existing process just because the application of document request control can be such a hassle.
5. The process of handling of internship must be upgraded especially with the current situation right now. It is not only academic units that must have an option for online advancement but also, it is proven that a web-based management system can improve the process of the internship.
6. Gathering feedback and conducting user training amidst pandemic is a challenging part for the proponent.

Nonetheless, despite all the challenges faced by the proponent, it is satisfying to see how the system is well quite received by the clients and is satisfied with its performance with some adjustments and further expansion in the future.

Maintenance Plan

The proponent decided to give the maintenance of the system to the University's Information and Communication Technology Department (ICTD) as this will be part of the contribution of the proponent to the growth of the University. The ICTD holds the hosting server of the University's website, thus, it is only appropriate to link the developed system to the main webpage for easier maintenance. Should there be any problems in the future, the proponent believes that the system is well-documented and is easier to revise.

Chapter VI

CONCLUSION

Based on the evaluation results gathered and findings mentioned above, the following conclusions were drawn:

1. The Internship management system for LPU-Cavite has provided a user-friendly interface that can be easily managed and operated by the users.
2. The developed system was developed based on the requirements given by the users.
3. The developed system was accepted by the target users with satisfaction in its performance, functionality, and ease of use.

Suggestions / Recommendations:

Based on the study results, it is suggested that the following recommendation listed below can help improve the features of the developed system:

1. Notifications through emails upon the intern's/applicant's approval could also be another option to secure that the application had been processed.
2. The system should ask for the specific address from the smallest details in the form of, Zip code, House no., Purok no., Barangay, Municipality, and Town.
3. Middle Initial/Name should be included for additional security.
4. A modal pop-up dialog box is highly recommended.

5. The internship management system uses a one-time upload for the applications, this having said, the respondents suggested that a batch upload would be better.
6. The Internship Management System is created for PC/Laptop use, that is why the layout mostly looks way better when viewed on a PC/Laptop, but since the respondents tried the system on a smartphone, they recommended that the system should also have enhanced layout for both mobile view and PC/Laptop view.

Positive Feedbacks:

1. The system is easy to use; there are no redundant questions or any irrelevant elements on the system.
2. The system is a great help for interns like us, it makes applications, submission of requirements faster and more convenient.

Chapter VII

FUTURE WORK

The web-based internship management system offers the University the idea that applying modernization to their current system can only bring good advantages to their business, provide progress to their staff, and bring convenience to their stakeholders. The internship is not just an added three or six-unit program to their curriculum, but it is the start of the career ground for the students. Thus, it is only fitting to have a better procedure and an efficient system that works for all its users.

Deployment Plan

Initially, the proponent has been deployed the system to a separate domain from the University while we wait for the approval of the Information and Communication Department to integrate the developed system into the existing platform.

The proponent, together with the ICTD, will test the environment on a local network first to check its vulnerability and conflicts that may arise. The team must document all potential risks to resolve the issues and administer necessary changes. User testing may be enforced again to verify if the system can now handle production issues with ease.

Once it is done, the proponent will now schedule the final deployment schedule in a live environment. It may need manpower during the critical stage of deployment to test the waters on how the system may perform on the actual platform.

User Training Plan

To ensure that all users of the developed system will have proper knowledge on the procedure of the said system, the proponent is recommending a training schedule for all the users – students, staff of the University, and the employers. This allows the proponent to lay out the goals of the system and what are each and everyone's role. A classroom-type seminar for the students to discuss the step-by-step procedure of the system and explain to them how the current procedure will be different from the existing one. Students must be informed that with the implementation of the developed system, the Center will enforce the current procedure to maximize its features.

The proponent also created a training schedule for the staff of the Center to assure that the officials are well-versed with the flow of the system. Accordingly, the staff will be the source of information for the students and employers in case there will be concerns with the process. The officials will be the ones to present to the accredited employers the process flow for the system once they have agreed to affiliate with the University.

Future Integration

Despite a satisfactory rating of the developed system during the user testing, the proponent would like to acknowledge the limitation of the study. These limitations can be considered as a way of implying that the system is open for future revisions and integrations.

The proponent wishes to expand the study of this system into incorporating the grading system of the University which is now being served by a separate web portal called AIMS. Through this, we can enhance the system that would help the instructor handling the internship to input their grades in one systematized system instead of using another portal. Though the proponent could have extended the study that would allow such dynamic, however, there needs to be a collaboration between the proponent and the existing portal. The web-based internship management system needs to be accustomed to the environment for a duration of time before it can be tested for further advancement.

Lastly, all templates and documents used in this system are templated to the current data files of the Center. By any means that should there be any revisions with these templates, the layout of the documents uploaded must be revised. Hence, if another study will be conducted, the adaptability of the layout of the reports can be considered for an upgrade.

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APPENDICES

System Usability Scale (SUS)

I think that I would like to use this system frequently. *

	1	2	3	4	5	
Strongly disagree	<input type="radio"/>	Strongly agree				

I found the system unnecessarily complex. *

	1	2	3	4	5	
Strongly disagree	<input type="radio"/>	Strongly agree				

I thought the system was easy to use. *

	1	2	3	4	5	
Strongly disagree	<input type="radio"/>	Strongly agree				

I think that I would need the support of a technical person to be able to use this system. *

	1	2	3	4	5	
Strongly disagree	<input type="radio"/>	Strongly agree				

I found the various functions in this system were well integrated. *

	1	2	3	4	5	
Strongly disagree	<input type="radio"/>	Strongly agree				

I thought there was too much inconsistency in this system. *

	1	2	3	4	5	
Strongly disagree	<input type="radio"/>	Strongly agree				

I would imagine that most people would learn to use this system very quickly. *

	1	2	3	4	5	
Strongly disagree	<input type="radio"/>	Strongly agree				

I found the system very cumbersome to use. *

	1	2	3	4	5	
Strongly disagree	<input type="radio"/>	Strongly agree				

I felt very confident using the system. *

	1	2	3	4	5	
Strongly disagree	<input type="radio"/>	Strongly agree				

I needed to learn a lot of things before I could get going with this system. *

	1	2	3	4	5	
Strongly disagree	<input type="radio"/>	Strongly agree				

Source Code

<https://github.com/alyssapaola/upou-internship-ms>

The screenshot shows a GitHub commit diff for user 'alyssapaola'. The commit message is 'Add files via upload' and the commit hash is '8d2c46a'. The commit was made 'now' and has '22 commits'. The diff shows a list of files and folders added to the repository, each with the message 'Add files via upload' and a timestamp.

File/Folder	Message	Time
admin	Add files via upload	1 hour ago
components	Add files via upload	39 minutes ago
css	Add files via upload	33 minutes ago
employer	Add files via upload	33 minutes ago
img	Add files via upload	30 minutes ago
lib	Add files via upload	5 minutes ago
login	Add files via upload	2 minutes ago
manager	Add files via upload	2 minutes ago
register	Add files via upload	2 minutes ago
staff	Add files via upload	2 minutes ago
student	Add files via upload	2 minutes ago
upload	Add files via upload	2 minutes ago
vendor	Add files via upload	now
composer.json	Add files via upload	now
composer.lock	Add files via upload	now
connect.php	Add files via upload	now
db_ojt.sql	Add files via upload	now
index.php	Add files via upload	now

User Manual Documentation

Figure 1. Homepage

The introductory page of the system. All users will go through this web page to access all the features of the system.

Figure 2. Log in page

All users will have the credentials that they need to navigate each of their accounts. Each account has features depending on their roles in the system.

A. Student

REGISTRATION

Student Number: *

First Name: *

Last Name: *

University / Office365 Email: *

College: *

Course: *

Year Level: *

Register

Already have an account? [Sign in](#)

Figure 3. Registration page

All students who are expected to have their internship for the next semester must register their information first to the system.

WEB IMS Login Credentials

Username: johnpaul.delacruz@lpunetwork.edu.ph
Password q84Y9g0O

Figure 4. Email Confirmation

After the registration, credentials will be sent to the student's Office365 account that will be used to log in to the system.

Orientation Schedule

Are you scheduled to have your internship?

As first step for internship procedure, all students who are scheduled to take their internship must attend the Orientation. In line with this, the Career Services and Industry Relations would like to invite you to their upcoming Orientation. Should you willing to participate, you may register from the schedules below:

Schedule 1	
Academic Term	Second Semester AY 2021 - 2022
Venue	Lemon Grass Studio
Date	January 17, 2022
Time	08:00 AM - 05:00 PM
Register	

Figure 5. Orientation Module

The first step of the internship process is the registration to the upcoming orientation. Students must register to their preferred schedule until one day before the schedule.

Success!

You have been registered to this event scheduled on:
January 17, 2022 from 08:00 AM to 05:00 PM
at Lemon Grass Studio

A confirmatory message will pop up after a successful registration

Orientation Attendance

Hello, John Paul, you are expected to attend the orientation for Second Semester AY 2021 - 2022. Check out the following details for your reference.
Note: Visit the portal after the orientation to mark your attendance and download/view your certificate.

Venue	Lemon Grass Studio
Date	January 17, 2022
Time	08:00 AM - 05:00 PM
Mark as Attended	

Students will only be able to mark their attendance after the event.

Orientation Attendance

Hello, John Paul, thank you for attending the orientation for Second Semester AY 2021 - 2022. You may now view or download your certificate for your reference, and proceed to the next step of internship.

[View/Download your certificate](#)

Students can view or download the certificate once they successfully mark their attendance.

Lyceum of the Philippines University – Cavite Campus
 Center for Career Services and Industry Relations
INTERNSHIP ORIENTATION
Certificate of Attendance

This certifies that **John Paul Dela Cruz**, attended the Internship Orientation conducted by the Center for Career Services & Industry Relations in preparation for Internship Program for **Second Semester AY 2021 - 2022**.

sgd.
 Lizandro O. Ferrer
 Director

Figure 6. The sample generated certificate

Internship Application

Second Semester, AY 2021 - 2022

[Change your information? Click here.](#)

Date Filed:	January 17, 2022
Application Number:	CCSIR-2022-001
Student Number:	2018-2-00001
Name:	John Paul Dela Cruz
Year and Course:	4th year Bachelor of Science in Information Technology
<u>Contact Information</u>	
Mobile Number:	09555443776
Primary Email Address:	johnpaul.delacruz@lpunetwork.edu.ph
Alternate Email Address:	jpgdelacruz@yahoo.com
Home Address:	General Trias, Cavite
<u>In case of emergency contact</u>	
Name:	Maria Dela Cruz
Relationship:	mother
Mobile Number:	09175563398
Home Address:	Manila
Internship Hours:	Choose here ▾
Application Photo	Browse... <input type="text"/>
<u>Internship Files</u>	
Internship Guidelines	<input type="button" value="Choose File"/> No file chosen
Internship Undertaking	<input type="button" value="Choose File"/> No file chosen
<u>Crediting of Hours (upload your supporting documents)</u>	
Employment	<input type="button" value="Choose File"/> No file chosen
Special Project	<input type="button" value="Choose File"/> No file chosen

Figure 7. The internship application module

Once the student confirms the attendance at the orientation, he/she can proceed to the application for the internship by submitting his/her information and necessary documents.

Internship Application

Second Semester, AY 2021 - 2022

Hello, John Paul, kindly take note of your application details below. Please wait for further instructions.

Application Number	CCSIR-2022-001
Student Number	2018-2-00001
Date Filed	January 14, 2022
Status	PENDING
Comment	-
View your Application	

The application status can be monitored through this page. Students can also view or download their application documents.

T-CSI-02C

LPU Center for Career Services and Industry Relations

Internship Application Second Semester, AY 2021 - 2022

Date Filed: January 14, 2022
Name: John Paul Dela Cruz
Year and Course: 4th year Bachelor of Science in Information Technology
Mobile Number: 09555443776
Primary Email Address: johnpaul.delacruz@lpunetwork.edu.ph
Alternate Email Address: jpdelacruz@yahoo.com
Home Address: General Trias, Cavite

Internship Hours: 500 hours

In case of emergency contact

Name:	Maria Dela Cruz	Relationship:	mother
Home Address:	Manila	Mobile Number:	09175563398

By affixing my signature on this form, I hereby acknowledge and certify that I have carefully read and understood the terms and conditions of the Data Privacy Policy of the Lyceum of the Philippines University (LPU). By providing personal information to LPU, I am confirming that the data is true and correct. I understand that LPU reserves the right to revise any decision made on the basis of the information I provided should the information be found to be untrue or incorrect. I likewise agree that any issue that may arise in connection with processing of my personal information will be settled amicably with LPU before resorting to appropriate arbitration or court proceedings within the Philippine jurisdiction. Finally, I am providing my voluntary consent and authorization to LPU and its duly authorized representatives to lawfully process my/my child's data/Information.

sgd.
John Paul Dela Cruz
Student

Figure 8. Sample generated internship application document

Job Application

Apply on different job listings here

Cloud Applications Intern

Open Text Philippines Inc.
Makati, Metro Manila

The Cloud Applications Intern Is An Individual Contributor Who Will Create And Update Technical... [Read More](#)

[Apply for this job](#)

Web Developer Intern

Leentech Network System
Tanza, Cavite

Project Internship Allow You To Get A Taste For What It's Really Like To Work In A Leading... [Read More](#)

[Apply for this job](#)

Figure 9. Job Application module

The job application module allows the student to choose from job listings of the accredited Host Training Establishments that fit the student’s program.

Cloud Applications Intern

Posted on January 09, 2022 by **Open Text Philippines Inc.**

Address:	Makati, Metro Manila
No. of Vacancies:	2
Description:	The Cloud Applications Intern Is An Individual Contributor Who Will Create And Update Technical Specifications, Forms And Maps Using OpenText Translation Software, Carry Out Integration Tasks To Deploy Forms And Maps To Pre-production Environments, And Setup Trading Partner Connectivity Using Common Communications Standards Such As Ftp, Http, AS2, And SFTP. vacancies
Skills	<small>enter your skills on the field below and click the spacebar after each keyword</small>
	<input style="width: 100%; height: 20px;" type="text"/>
Why should we hire you?	
	<div style="border: 1px solid #ccc; height: 40px; width: 100%;"></div>

Figure 10 Application form for job module

Students are allowed to apply on different job applications but it’s the discretion of the employer to approve it or not.

Hello, John Paul [f](#) [@](#)

WEB·IMS HOME ORIENTATION ▾ APPLICATION ▾ JOB VACANCIES ▾ REPORTS ▾ PROFILE LOGOUT

Templates

Downloads templates that will be used for internship

Show entries Search:

No	Template Name	Template Description	Template Category
1	Internship Guidelines	for signature of the student and parent	Prelim
2	Internship Undertaking	for notarization	Prelim

Showing 1 to 2 of 2 entries

Previous **1** Next

Figure 11. Templates module

This module allows the students to download the internship templates that they need throughout the internship process.

Hello, John Paul [f](#) [@](#)

WEB·IMS HOME ORIENTATION ▾ APPLICATION ▾ JOB VACANCIES ▾ REPORTS ▾ **PROFILE** LOGOUT

Profile

Edit your profile that matches with your basic information

Basic Information (click to show/hide panel)

Contact Information (click to show/hide panel)

Education Information (click to show/hide panel)

Emergency Contact Information (click to show/hide panel)

Change Password (click to show/hide panel)

Figure 12. Profile module

Student's information can be modified through this page

B. Manager / Head of the Center

The following modules are designed only for a supervisory role. Their rights include setting up the orientation details, managing the accounts of every user, and assignment of different programs or section to its staff.

WEB-IMS Hello, Manager [f](#) [@](#)

HOME INTERNSHIP PORTAL ▾ JOB PORTAL ▾ CONFIGURATION ▾ LOGOUT

Faculty Assignment

Manages staff/faculty assignment of sections

Select Staff ▾ Filter Add

Show entries Search:

No	Staff Name	Sections Assigned	Action
1	Staff Staff	IT 401	Delete
2	Staff2 Staff2	AC 401	Delete

Showing 1 to 2 of 2 entries

Previous 1 Next

Figure 13. Faculty Assignment module

This feature allows the manager to assign the programs or sections to its staff. Should there be any modification on the assignment, the manager can only delete the current assignment.

Internship Hours

Modifies the internship hours record per courses based on curriculum

Select College ▾ Filter Add

Show 10 ▾ entries Search:

No	College	Course	Internship Hours	Action
1	College of Allied Medical Science	Bachelor of Science in Pharmacy	200	Edit Delete
2	College of Arts and Science	Bachelor of Arts in Communication	300	Edit Delete
3	College of Business Administration	Bachelor of Science in Accountancy	400	Edit Delete
4	College of Engineering, Computer Studies and Architecture	Bachelor of Science in Information Technology	500	Edit Delete
5	College of Nursing	Bachelor of Science in Nursing	200	Edit Delete

Showing 1 to 5 of 5 entries Previous **1** Next

Figure 14. Configuration of Internship Hours

This feature allows the manager to set up the number of internship hours of different programs.

Create New ✕

College *

Choose here ▾

Course *

Choose here ▾

Internship Hours *

Insert
Close

The user must choose from the options under the College section and its respective course and supply the necessary internship hours.

WEB·IMS Hello, Manager

HOME INTERNSHIP PORTAL ▾ JOB PORTAL ▾ CONFIGURATION ▾ LOGOUT

Credit Hours

Modifies the internship credit hours record

Select College ▾ Filter Add

Show 10 entries Search:

No	Credit Description	Credit Hours	College	Action
1	Employment	100	College of Engineering, Computer Studies and Architecture	Edit Delete
2	Special Project	250	College of Engineering, Computer Studies and Architecture	Edit Delete

Showing 1 to 2 of 2 entries

Previous 1 Next

Figure 15. Configuration for number of hours credited

Relatively, this feature allows the manager to supply details that are allowed to be credited from the student’s application with a corresponding number of hours.

Create New ×

Credit Description *

Credit Hours *

College *

Choose here
▾

Insert
Close

The necessary fields for this feature help the manager and staff to describe the credit to be taken from the application.

Orientation Record

Manages the records of current and past orientation

Select Academic Term ▾ Filter Add

Show 10 ▾ entries Search:

No	Academic Term	Venue	Date	Time	Action
1	Second Semester AY 2021 - 2022	Lemon Grass Studio	January 17, 2022	08:00 AM - 05:00 PM	Edit Hide Delete
2	Second Semester AY 2021 - 2022	University Auditorium	January 18, 2022	08:00 AM - 05:00 PM	Edit Hide Delete
3	First Semester AY 2020 - 2021	University Auditorium	October 12, 2021	08:00 AM - 05:00 PM	Edit Delete
4	First Semester AY 2020 - 2021	Lemon Grass Studio	October 11, 2021	08:00 AM - 05:00 PM	Edit Delete
5	First Semester AY 2021 - 2022	Lemon Grass Studio	October 13, 2021	08:00 AM - 05:00 PM	Edit Delete
6	First Semester AY 2021 - 2022	University Auditorium	October 14, 2021	08:00 AM - 05:00 PM	Edit Delete
7	Second Semester AY 2020 - 2021	University Auditorium	December 07, 2020	12:00 AM - 11:30 PM	Edit Delete

Showing 1 to 7 of 7 entries

Previous 1 Next

Figure 16. Orientation Record module

This module is featured on both the manager and staff of the Center to schedule the Orientation of the students, which is the first part of the internship process

Create New ×

Academic Term *

Venue *

Orientation Date *

Orientation Start Time *

Orientation End Time *

Publish?

Insert Close

Hello, Manager [f](#) [@](#)

[HOME](#)
[INTERNSHIP PORTAL](#)
[JOB PORTAL](#)
[CONFIGURATION](#)
[LOGOUT](#)

WEB·IMS

Students

Displays all students enrolled in the system

Show entries
 Search:

No	Student Number	First Name	Last Name	College	Course	Action
1	2018-2-00001	John Paul	Dela Cruz	COECSA	BSIT	<input type="button" value="View"/> <input type="button" value="Edit"/> <input type="button" value="Archive"/> <input type="button" value="Delete"/>

Showing 1 to 1 of 1 entries

Figure 17. Student Management module

Necessary fields indicate the orientation details for students' information. This module is a feature to both the manager and the staff as they can administer the student's account – add, modify, and delete them whichever is applicable.

Create New Account ×

Student Number *

First Name *

Last Name *

Username *

Password

College: *

Course: *

Year Level: *

Suspended account

The previous figure shows the needed data to create an account for the student. An email confirmation will be sent to the user after this registration.

The screenshot shows the 'WEB·IMS' header with navigation links: HOME, INTERNSHIP PORTAL, JOB PORTAL, CONFIGURATION, and LOGOUT. The user is logged in as 'Hello, Manager'. The main section is titled 'Templates' with a subtitle 'Manages templates that will be used for internship'. There is an 'Add' button and a search bar. A table lists two templates:

No	Template Name	Template Description	Template Category	Action
1	Internship Guidelines	for signature of the student and parent	Prelim	View Edit Hide Delete
2	Internship Undertaking	for notarization	Prelim	View Edit Hide Delete

Below the table, it says 'Showing 1 to 2 of 2 entries' and has 'Previous', '1', and 'Next' navigation buttons.

Figure 18. Template Management module

This module is also present in the staff account, where they could upload the necessary internship templates needed by the student.

The 'Create New' form includes the following fields:

- Template Name ***: A text input field.
- Template Description ***: A text area for a detailed description.
- Template Category ***: A dropdown menu with 'Choose here' selected.
- File ***: A file upload field with a 'Choose File' button and the text 'No file chosen'.
- Publish?**: A checkbox to indicate if the template should be published.

At the bottom right, there are 'Insert' and 'Close' buttons.

Description of the templates to be uploaded are necessary fields for this template management feature.

Figure 19. Company Profile feature

All accredited Host Training Establishments will be registered in the portal through this feature. Details needed include the HTE's basic information, terms of the contract, and the uploaded Memorandum of Agreement. Once, an HTE's contract hasn't been renewed, the manager can remove the company from the list temporarily, or until such time, the contract will be renewed.

The screenshot shows the 'COMPANY PROFILE' registration form. At the top right, it says 'Hello, Manager' with social media icons and a 'BACK TO HOME' button. The form fields are: 'Company Name *' (text input), 'Description *' (text area), 'Province *' (dropdown menu with 'Choose here'), 'City *' (dropdown menu with 'Choose here'), and 'Floor/Unit/Room (optional)' (text input).

The figure shows the sample registration form of the HTE to be included in the pool of accredited HTEs displayed in the system.

Hello, Manager

WEB·IMS HOME INTERNSHIP PORTAL ▾ JOB PORTAL ▾ CONFIGURATION ▾ LOGOUT

Employer Information

Displays the information of enrolled users of affiliated industry partners

[Add](#)

Show entries Search:

No	First Name	Last Name	Username	Company Affiliated	Action
1	Employer	Employer	employer@lpu.edu.ph	Leentech Network System	View Edit Archive Delete
2	Employer2	Employer2	employer2@lpu.edu.ph	Open Text Philippines Inc.	View Edit Archive Delete

Showing 1 to 2 of 2 entries

[Previous](#) [1](#) [Next](#)

Figure 20. Employer Information module

Once the information of the HTE is registration into the system, the manager will now create the account credentials of every staff of the HTE that is needed to be registered as well to the system. One or two people may be allowed to be handed an account to maintain the job postings of their company.

Create New Account ×

First Name *

Last Name *

Password

Username *

Suspended account

Company Affiliated *

Department *

The previous figure displays the registration form of the employer which includes its basic information and the company he/she is affiliated to. The manager must note that the HTE must be registered into the system first before its employees.

WEB-IMS Hello, Manager [f](#) [@](#)

HOME INTERNSHIP PORTAL ▾ JOB PORTAL ▾ CONFIGURATION ▾ LOGOUT

Company Department

Modifies general department of a company

[Add](#)

Show entries Search:

No	Department	Action
1	Administration	Edit Delete
2	Executive	Edit Delete
3	Finance	Edit Delete
4	Human Resources	Edit Delete
5	IT	Edit Delete
6	Marketing	Edit Delete
7	Public Relations	Edit Delete

Figure 21. Configuration of Company department

A simple configuration feature which is needed for categorizing the accredited employers.

WEB-IMS Hello, Manager [f](#) [@](#)

HOME INTERNSHIP PORTAL ▾ JOB PORTAL ▾ CONFIGURATION ▾ LOGOUT

Sections

Modifies the details of each section

[Filter](#) [Add](#)

Show entries Search:

No	Section Name	College	Course	Action
1	IT 401	College of Engineering, Computer Studies and Architecture	Bachelor of Science in Information Technology	Edit Hide Delete
2	AC 401	College of Business Administration	Bachelor of Science in Accountancy	Edit Hide Delete

Showing 1 to 2 of 2 entries

Previous 1 Next

This feature provides the manager the right to create the section for each program.

WEB·IMS Hello, Manager [f](#) [@](#)

[HOME](#)
[INTERNSHIP PORTAL](#)
[JOB PORTAL](#)
[CONFIGURATION](#)
[LOGOUT](#)

Users

Displays the units' list of users

[Add](#)

Show entries Search:

No	First Name	Last Name	Username	Action
1	Staff	Staff	staff@lpu.edu.ph	View Edit Archive Delete
2	Staff2	Staff2	staff2@lpu.edu.ph	View Edit Archive Delete

Showing 1 to 2 of 2 entries (filtered from 7 total entries)

[Previous](#)
[1](#)
[Next](#)

Figure 22. Users Management module

This module is similar to the student management module (Figure 17) except that it only displays the list of users whose role is the staff/employees of the University.

C. The staff of the Center

The primary role of this user is to manage the applications and documents submitted by the students. The features presented on this account allow the staff of the Center to generate reports that correspond to the data provided.

Hello, Staff [f](#) [@](#)

WEB·IMS HOME INTERNSHIP MODULE ▾ CONFIGURATION ▾ LOGOUT

Student Orientation Record

Displays all attendance record of the students

Select Academic Term ▾ Select College ▾ Select Attendance Record ▾ Filter Add

Show 10 ▾ entries Search:

No	Registration Number	Student Number	College	Orientation Schedule	Academic Term	Status	Action
1	REG-2022-001	2018-2-00001	COECSA	January 17, 2022 / 08:00 AM - 05:00 PM	Second Semester AY 2021 - 2022	Attended	View Edit

Showing 1 to 1 of 1 entries

Previous 1 Next

Figure 23. Orientation Record module

This module will just allow the staff to view the orientation attendance status of a particular student if there is a need to counteract. It also authorized the staff to bypass the attendance of the student should there be a need to mark its attendance with a proper excuse on the student's part.

Hello, Staff [f](#) [@](#)

WEB·IMS HOME INTERNSHIP MODULE ▾ CONFIGURATION ▾ LOGOUT

Internship Application Record

Displays all application of the students

Select Academic Term ▾ Select College ▾ Select Status ▾ Filter

Show 10 ▾ entries Search:

No	Application Number	Student Number	College	Academic Term	Status	Action
1	CCSIR-2022-001	2018-2-00001	COECSA	Second Semester, AY 2021 - 2022	Approved	View

Showing 1 to 1 of 1 entries

Previous 1 Next

Figure 24. Internship Application module

Contrary to the previous module, this feature is needed for the Center's approval whether the submitted documents and information matches with the standard and adheres to the policies.

Hello, Staff [f](#) [@](#)

WEB·IMS HOME INTERNSHIP MODULE ▾ CONFIGURATION ▾ LOGOUT

Assigned Students

Displays all students assigned to the faculty/staff

Select Academic Term ▾ Select Section ▾ **Filter**

Show entries Search:

No	Student Number	Name	Course	Section	Job Application Status
1	2018-2-00001	John Paul Dela Cruz	BSIT	IT 401	Pending Application

Showing 1 to 1 of 1 entries (filtered from 0 total entries)

Previous **1** Next

Figure 25. Classlist Management module

Once the manager already assigned your account to a specific section or program, the user for this role will now view the students included on the class list for monitoring of their internship status.

D. Host Training Establishment

This feature will only be activated with the University’s approval. This provides the employee of the accredited HTE to manage their job listings and job applications of the students.

Hello, Employer [f](#) [@](#)

WEB·IMS HOME JOB APPLICATION CONFIGURATION ▾ LOGOUT

Job Application

Manages all job listings posted by the employer

Show entries Search:

No	Job Title	Pending	Approved	Disapproved	Total
1	Finance Trainee	0	0	0	0
2	Web Developer Intern	0	0	0	0

Showing 1 to 2 of 2 entries (filtered from 0 total entries)

Previous **1** Next

Figure 26. Job Application module

The previous figure displays their active job listings alongside the number of applications – approved, pending, and rejected – for easier monitoring. On this feature as well, the HTE can approve or reject the application based on the information and questions provided.

WEB·IMS Hello, Employer

HOME JOB APPLICATION CONFIGURATION ▾ LOGOUT

Job Listing

Manages all job listings posted by the employer

[Add](#)

Show entries Search:

No	Job Title	No. of Vacancies	Status	Action
1	Finance Trainee	5	Active	View Edit Unpublish Delete
2	Web Developer Intern	5	Active	View Edit Unpublish Delete

Showing 1 to 2 of 2 entries (filtered from 0 total entries)

Previous **1** Next

Figure 27 Job listing module

This feature focuses on the job postings of the HTE. It allows them to add or modify the listings whichever applies to the given scenario.

JOB POSTING

Job Title *

Description *

No. of Vacancies *

Applicable for Courses *

With Salary/Allowance Provided?

[Post](#)

The needed information to establish an active job listing.

COMPANY PROFILE

Company Name *

Description *

Province *

City *

Floor/Unit/Room *

Email Address *

HTEs can update their information should there be any changes to it.

E. System Administrator

This user provides the foundation of the system. Activities such as users' management – only for their staff and their co-managers, the configuration of the colleges, venues, and the program offered by the University.

Hello, Admin [f](#) [@](#)

WEB·IMS HOME CONFIGURATION ▾ LOGOUT

Users

Displays all users of the system - students, administrators, and industry partners

Select Role ▾ Filter Add

Show 10 ▾ entries Search:

No	First Name	Last Name	Username	Action
1	Manager	Manager	manager@pu.edu.ph	View Edit Archive Delete
2	Staff	Staff	staff@pu.edu.ph	View Edit Archive Delete
3	Staff2	Staff2	staff2@pu.edu.ph	View Edit Archive Delete

Showing 1 to 3 of 3 entries (filtered from 7 total entries)

Previous 1 Next

Figure 28. User management module

The only difference for this module compared to other user management modules from the other users of the system, is it displays all the users registered to the system.

Hello, Admin [f](#) [@](#)

WEB·IMS HOME CONFIGURATION ▾ LOGOUT

Colleges

Modifies the details of each department/colleges

[Add](#)

Show 10 ▾ entries Search:

No	Short Name	Full Name	Action
1	CAMS	College of Allied Medical Science	Edit Hide Delete
2	CAS	College of Arts and Science	Edit Hide Delete
3	CBA	College of Business Administration	Edit Hide Delete
4	COECSA	College of Engineering, Computer Studies and Architecture	Edit Hide Delete
5	CON	College of Nursing	Edit Hide Delete

Showing 1 to 5 of 5 entries

Previous 1 Next

Figure 29 College record module

Courses

Modifies the details of each courses

Select College ▼ Filter Add

Show 10 entries Search:

No	Short Name	Full Name	College Description	Action
1	ABCOMM	Bachelor of Arts in Communication	College of Arts and Science	Edit Hide Delete
2	BSA	Bachelor of Science in Accountancy	College of Business Administration	Edit Hide Delete
3	BSIT	Bachelor of Science in Information Technology	College of Engineering, Computer Studies and Architecture	Edit Hide Delete
4	BSN	Bachelor of Science in Nursing	College of Nursing	Edit Hide Delete
5	BSPH	Bachelor of Science in Pharmacy	College of Allied Medical Science	Edit Hide Delete

Showing 1 to 5 of 5 entries

Figure 30. Courses record module

The administrator will be the one to supply the necessary colleges and its courses involved in this system.

WEB·IMS Hello, Admin [f](#) [@](#)
HOME CONFIGURATION ▼ LOGOUT

Academic Term

Modifies the details of each academic term

Add

Show 10 entries Search:

No	Description	Action
1	Second Semester AY 2021 - 2022	Edit Unset to Current Hide Delete
2	First Semester AY 2021 - 2022	Edit Hide Delete
3	First Semester AY 2020 - 2021	Edit Hide Delete
4	Second Semester AY 2020 - 2021	Edit Hide Delete

Showing 1 to 4 of 4 entries

Previous
1
Next

Figure 31 Academic term record module

The administrator will be the one to set the academic terms for record-seeking purposes.

Venues

Modifies the details of each venues

[Add](#)Show entriesSearch:

No	Venue Name/Description	Action
1	Lemon Grass Studio	Edit Hide Delete
2	University Auditorium	Edit Hide Delete

Showing 1 to 2 of 2 entries

[Previous](#) [1](#) [Next](#)

Figure 32 Venue's record module

In connection with the Orientation record module (Figure 23), the administrator must enable the venues for display in the system. This feature can help the administrator set the said venues.